

CUSTODES

**A Certification approach for dynamic, agile and reUSable assessment
fOr composite systems of ICT proDucts, servicEs and processeS**

Project Overview

Cybersecurity certification as introduced by the EU Cybersecurity Act (EUCSA) will play a crucial role in increasing the trust to and security of ICT Products, ICT Services and ICT Processes. Cybersecurity certification is a complex process, posing a variety of challenges to the different interested parties. The envisioned CUSTODES system is comprised of a variety of components with the aim to provide trustworthy, cost-effective, agile and portable conformity assessment capabilities, to a variety of interested parties, covering multiple Assurance levels of Composite ICT products or ICT services.

Project Objectives

- ✓ Promote the scalable, agile and verifiable certification of Composite Targets of Evaluation (TOE), towards ensuring and fostering the protection, resilience of the ICT products, ICT services and ICT processes, converting Europe into a Trustworthy Certified Digital Ecosystem.
- ✓ Facilitate the accurate definition, evaluation and classification of complex and highly interconnected (Composite) TOE.
- ✓ Optimize, automate and facilitate the conformity assessment of Composite TOE ensuring compliance and mitigating potential compliance breaches.
- ✓ Establish and guarantee the trust relationships in the Certification process.
- ✓ Enable robustness and sustainability of the self-assessment (i.e. audit/testing) throughout TOE Lifecycles.
- ✓ Promote and enable the trustable and transparent sharing and reuse of certification related information.
- ✓ Development, validation and demonstration of CUSTODES framework through its application to large-scale real scenarios/conditions - Market validation and Roll out.
- ✓ Provide tailored certification-related recommendations.

The Consortium

The project unites 16 partners from 11 countries:

Sweden, Germany, France, Italy,
Belgium, Ireland, Spain, Greece,
Cyprus, Netherlands, Switzerland

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